

Scholarly persuasion: Analyzing rhetorical structures and linguistic features in scholarship motivation letters

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This qualitative study aimed to analyze the rhetorical structures and linguistic features of motivation letters written by scholarship awardees when they applied to scholarship programs. 20 motivation letters written by former students of Universitas Islam Negeri Ar-Raniry (UINAR) and Universitas Syiah Kuala (USK) were used for this study. The motivation letters were examined using a seven-step analysis model as a procedure to analyze genres in a discourse. The results showed five out of seven moves were used in the motivation letters. However, the way the students used the moves varied. Move 1 (establishing credentials) and Move 2 (introducing candidature) were found in 19 motivation letters while other moves were found variously in 1 to 4 motivation letters. This study concluded that the obligatory moves used in the motivation letters are (a) establishing credentials and (b) introducing candidature. Linguistic features used in the data were personal pronouns, present simple tense, present perfect tense, passive voice, adverbs, and modals.

Keywords: Genre; Genre Analysis; Linguistic Features; Motivation Letter; Rhetorical Structures; Scholarship Awardees

1. Introduction

Writing for academic purposes is essential for university students, as their academic performance is primarily evaluated through written assignments (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2014). Nga (2009) emphasizes that writing is the most critical language skill for students, particularly when it comes to assessments like final examinations, academic reports, and theses. However, writing can be especially challenging for English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners (Salmani Nodoushan, 2016), as they often struggle to convey their ideas effectively and organize their thoughts into coherent structures (Alavi &

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Salmani Nodoushan, 2004; Birjandi et al., 2004; Isgiarno et al., 2020; Salmani Nodoushan, 2009). Flynn and Stainthorp (2006) note that writing becomes even more difficult when students have to think and write in a second language (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2007b, 2007c, 2015).

Beyond academic settings, writing skills are also crucial in professional environments (Salmani Nodoushan, 2023b). One particular form of writing that students may encounter is the motivation letter, which is often required when applying for scholarships. A motivation letter allows applicants to express why they are a suitable candidate for a specific program or scholarship. The content typically reflects the applicant's professional and personal growth by looking at past experiences and future aspirations (Khakimova & Tolstykh, 2023). Despite its importance, many EFL students face difficulties in various stages of the writing process, such as outlining, gathering ideas, drafting, and constructing coherent sentences due to limited vocabulary and grammatical knowledge, spelling errors, and difficulties in word choice (Alisha et al., 2019; Belkhir & Benyelles, 2017; Bisriyah, 2022; Salmani Nodoushan, 2007a, 2018).

The studies that analyzed the rhetorical structures of motivation letters are less available in the literature. Given the challenges EFL students face in writing motivation letters, our study seeks to analyze the rhetorical structures and linguistic features of motivation letters written by successful scholarship applicants. Specifically, we focus on alumni and alumnae of Universitas Islam Negeri Ar-Raniry (UINAR) and Universitas Syiah Kuala (USK) who have been awarded scholarships. Our research is guided by the following questions:

- (1) What rhetorical structures are used by former UINAR and USK students in motivation letters for scholarships?
- (2) What are the linguistic features used by former UINAR and USK students in motivation letters for scholarships?

2. Background

Being part of the discipline of English for specific purposes (cf. Johns & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015; Salmani Nodoushan, 2020), rhetorical structure analysis is often conducted to analyze the structure of texts—in accordance with the guidelines of a descriptive model known as the Rhetorical Structure Theory (RST); rhetorical structure analysis focuses on the hierarchical relationships between different segments (Mann & Thompson, 1988; see also Bhatia & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015).

According to RST, texts are composed of groups of clauses arranged hierarchically, connected through rhetorical relations, which typically involve a nucleus (the central idea) and a satellite (supporting information) (Thompson & Mann, 1987). Beware that this view of text differs from the

'extended' view of text upheld by sociosemiotics which encompasses intertextuality, Foucauldian panopticon, linguistic landscape, etc. (cf. Sari, et al., 2024; Salmani Nodoushan, 2021, 2023a). RST highlights the importance of the nucleus-satellite patterns of a text in shaping its overall communicative purpose and emphasizes that text structure serves a functional role in communication (Mann & Thompson, 1987). This framework has been widely applied in fields such as artificial intelligence, computational linguistics, and discourse analysis, providing understandings into how text organization influences meaning (Thompson & Mann, 1987). More recently, its application has expanded to include areas like computer-supported collaborative learning (CSCL), where it helps in understanding how text structures can facilitate learning in digital environments (Allaymoun, 2015).

Building on frameworks like RST, genre analysis further allows for the examination of how specific types of writing, such as motivation letters, adhere to distinct structural patterns and communicative functions. The process of genre analysis helps to understand how different forms of writing, such as motivation letters, follow specific structures and conventions (Salmani Nodoushan, 2011). Bhatia (1993) proposed a seven-step model for genre analysis, which serves as a guide for analyzing texts based on their context, structure, and purpose. These steps include:

1. Placing the given genre-text in a situational context
2. Surveying existing literature
3. Refining the situational/contextual analysis
4. Selecting corpus
5. Studying the institutional context
6. Levels of linguistic analysis
7. Specialist information in genre analysis

Depending on the focus of the analysis, not all steps are required, but understanding the genre is critical to analyzing its rhetorical structure. Bhatia's (1993) model has been used to analyze various genres, including job application letters, which share similarities with motivation letters. In both genres, rhetorical structures play a key role in presenting the candidature and persuading the reader of the candidate's value.

Studies on the analysis of rhetorical structures of different written discourses have been conducted by various scholars (e.g., Khakbaz & Salmani Nodoushan, 2011; Montazeran & Salmani Nodoushan, 2012; Salmani Nodoushan, 2012, 2023b; Yazdanpanah et al., 2021). Jogthong (2001) revealed that advanced learners have difficulties with written academic discourse at the level of rhetorical structure. Maasum et al. (2007) looked into job application letters written in English by Malaysian graduates. Moreover, some scholars

spotlighted the analysis of rhetorical structures in research articles (e.g., Ab Rahim et al., 2013; Kanoksilapatham, 2005; Pashapour et al., 2018), and online advertisements (e.g., Labrador et al., 2014). These studies have analyzed the moves or the stages used in developing online advertisements and research articles.

Arguing that it is difficult to write an essay without a clear framework to rely on, Askehave and Swales (2001) stated that the communicative purpose of written discourse is not always obvious and clear. Sometimes, it may have more than one purpose or multiple purposes. Knowing (a) the communicative purpose, (b) rhetorical structures, and (c) linguistic features of a text can help students consciously structure their texts and develop effective control for specific purposes. Besides the importance of knowing the procedure of genre analysis, it is also necessary to understand the aspects of genre that can be analyzed in a discourse which include the purpose, structure, and language features (Rose & Martin, 2012).

As one type of genre within the academy, motivation letters play a pivotal role in academic and professional applications, allowing individuals to convey their qualifications for specific programs or positions. Studies indicate that these letters generally follow four rhetorical moves: (a) explaining the reasons for applying, (b) outlining objectives, (c) persuading the reader, and (d) highlighting future expectations (Urizar Ocampo & Velásquez Upegui, 2023). The content frequently highlights the applicant's professional and personal growth by reflecting on past achievements and future goals (Khakimova & Tolstykh, 2023). While applicants mainly express autonomous motivation, this factor does not significantly differentiate successful from unsuccessful candidates (Wouters et al., 2014). Furthermore, a motivation letter is a scholarship requirement letter or essay to describe why a student is a perfect fit for a certain degree program. Motivation letters can be defined as occluded or semi-occluded written genres (Samraj & Monk, 2008). In this connection, Swales (1996) has defined genres in the academy as typically formal documents that are rarely part of the public record and intended for a specific audience. In the last decade, studying at, and graduating from, overseas universities have increased gradually. It is not only about prestige but also about an A-list graduate in the working environment.

As such, writing a motivation letter is one of the academic writing requirements needed to apply for a scholarship. In addition to the rhetorical structures, linguistic features play a significant role in writing motivation letters. Tenses are particularly important in these letters, as they indicate the writer's experience and future aspirations. Tatsanajamsuk (2017) notes that motivation letters frequently employ a variety of tenses, including the past simple, present simple, present progressive, present perfect, and present

perfect progressive. Each tense serves a specific function, such as highlighting past achievements or current qualifications, and can impact how a motivation letter is perceived by the reader.

Swales and Feak (1994) also emphasize the importance of objectivity in formal writing. They argue that writers should maintain an impersonal tone by using passive voice constructions and avoiding personal pronouns. This helps to focus the letter on the applicant's qualifications rather than their personal opinions or emotions. Additionally, modals, adverbs, and specific vocabulary choices are critical in conveying the writer's intentions and establishing the desired tone.

In an earlier study of non-native speaker writing at graduated level, Allison et al. (1998) pinpointed difficulties at (a) the macro-level of the thesis; (b) the micro-level of paragraph organization, arguments, strength of claims; and (c) the surface level of grammatical structure and mechanics of writing. In relevance to this research, the macro-level relates to the rhetorical structure of the writing while the micro-level relates to its linguistic features. Owing to the fact that exposure to genres is a rare thing for students even in universities, the students struggled to choose vocabulary appropriately, organize the rhetorical structures properly according to the topic or the writing purposes, and use grammatical structure accurately (Rahman, 2011). Tenses always employed in the application letters consisted of past simple, present simple, present progressive, present perfect, and present perfect progressive (Tatsanajamsuk, 2017). Swales and Feak (1994) also assert that writers need to maintain objectivity in their writing and focus on the appropriate use of pronouns and impersonal passives. Based on the explanation above, the linguistic features mostly found in the motivation/application letter may consist of some features such as pronouns, present tenses, perfect tenses, passive voices, modals, and adverbs which are analyzed in this research.

3. Method

3.1. Participants & Design

A descriptive qualitative method was used in this study to explore the patterns within textual data (Colorafi & Evans, 2016). To systematically identify these patterns and characteristics, content analysis was employed. Ary et al. (2002) describe content analysis as a research method applied to written or visual materials to identify specified characteristics, and it is instrumental in revealing patterns in recorded communication. This method involves the systematic collection and examination of data from texts, whether written, oral, or visual, to uncover underlying trends and themes.

Bogdan and Biklen (2003) state that qualitative data are gathered in the form of words or pictures rather than numbers. In this qualitative research, the primary source of data was documents—which included 20 motivation letters written by scholarship awardees who had applied to a scholarship program. The motivation letters were varied from former UINAR and USK students who had been awarded scholarships to universities overseas. The 20 motivation letters were selected mainly because of their availability to be collected and analyzed by the researchers. Besides, the characteristics of the motivation letters must be the ones that granted the scholarship. They had been written by UINAR and USK alumni in the past three years.

3.2. Procedure

The documentation method is used in this research. Documentation includes collecting public and/or private records, for example, newspapers, meeting minutes, and letters (Creswell, 2012). We collected 20 motivation letters written by scholarship awardee students when they applied to a scholarship program such as Lembaga Pengelola Dana Pendidikan (LPDP), Australia Awards Scholarship (AAS), and Deutscher Akademischer Austauschdienst Scholarship (DAAD). The letters collected varied from former UINAR and USK students who had been awarded scholarships to universities overseas. Finally, we analyzed the documents using five steps of genre analysis adopted from the seven-step genre analysis model by Bhatia (1993) to answer both of the research questions. The steps that we used are (a) surveying existing literature, (b) selecting corpus, (c) studying the institutional context, (d) analyzing levels of linguistics, and (e) consulting specialist information. Out of the five steps, the fourth step is specifically intended to analyze the rhetorical structures and linguistic features of the motivational letters.

4. Results

4.1. Rhetorical structures

Based on 20 motivation letters that have been analyzed, Motivation Letter 1 had used only Move 1 in the letter. Seven motivational letters had used Move 1 and Move 2. Eight motivation letters had started with Move 2 in the letters and then proceeded with Move 1. By way of contrast, 2 motivational letters had started with Move 2 in the letters but had then jumped to Move 7. We noticed only one motivation letter that had used five rhetorical moves (i.e., Moves 2, 1, 4, 6, 7—in that order), and one motivation letter that had used four rhetorical moves (i.e., Moves 2, 1, 7, and 6—in that order). Likewise, two motivation letters had used Moves 2 and 7, and only one motivation letter had used only one move, that is Move 1. Twelve of the twenty motivation letters (60%) had started the letter by using Move 2 instead of Move 1. The others had started

with Move 1, which is establishing credentials. However, the way the writers had presented Move 1 was different. The example of Move 1 is presented in Excerpt 1.

Excerpt 1

An example of Move 1

Dear Sir or Madam,

The need for improving the standard of living of citizens in a developing region such as Aceh province in Indonesia persists. The most recent report from BRR/BPS/WB (2008)¹ shows that 26.5% of Acehnese households live below the poverty line even though the province has a lot of natural resources, and other geographical and geological advantages. Financial service organizations or institutions such as Banks, Rural Banks, Microfinance Institutions and the government will need to combine forces to address factors of poverty. The different agencies will be required to develop models that can be used to drive the economic growth to improve the living standard of members of the community in a sustainable way. One of the prerequisites for this economic growth is the availability of qualified human resources, such as professional accountants who can develop and maintain internal and external systems that can provide high quality services for the people while ensuring adequate controls and transparency.

As for Move 2, introducing candidature, we found it in 19 out of 20 motivation letters, as shown in Excerpt 2.

Excerpt 2

An example of Move 2

Dear Selection Committee,

I am taking the liberty of introducing myself, my name is _____ a junior lecturer at Accounting Department of _____ Faculty of _____ University, Banda Aceh - Indonesia. Regarding my area of expertise, my predominantly vocal point is financial accounting and sharia accounting, including Islamic finance and banking, where my Bachelor's degree Thesis discussed the implementation of Good Corporate Governance (GCG) in Islamic and Conventional rural banks (BPR/S) in Aceh province. Moreover, I also interested in the development of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in related to financial access and microfinance, as well as the business management, where my Master graduate Thesis focused on the role of Islamic dan Conventional rural banks (BPR/S) financing in developing the SMEs in Aceh during the post-tsunami period. Therefore, I am eager to apply for this research training scholarship in order to enhance my qualification in research ability, particularly statistical model through discussion with expert professors in your universities and attending several seminars related to finance and banking issues.

Moves 1 and 2 (i.e., first and second moves) are very important because they present the candidates' strengths to meet the requirements of a prospective scholarship. That is the reason why both of them were presented in all of the motivation letters that we analyzed. Since there are some steps in performing Move 1 and Move 2, many of the students had used different steps (more explanation in the discussion section below). We hardly found other moves in the motivation letters.

There was no motivation letter with Move 3 (offering incentives) present in it. Only two motivation letters had included Move 4—which is enclosing the documents. Two motivation letters had used Move 6—soliciting a response. None of the motivation letters had used Move 5—using a pressure tactic. The last move is ending politely which was found in four motivation letters.

4.2. Linguistic features

Our study found some language features that were mostly used in the motivation letters by the scholarship awardees participating in this study. They are (a) personal pronouns, (b) present simple, (c) passive voices, (d) perfect tenses, (e) adverbs, and (f) modal. In analyzing the motivation letters, a notable trend emerged: all writers consistently employed the personal pronoun “I” in their expressions. This pattern is exemplified in Motivation Letter 6, where the writer consistently used “I” to reference himself/herself. For instance:

- I have a passion for becoming a professional-independent financial practitioner.
- I have been inspired by the work of Muhammad Yunus with his Greemen Bank project in Sri Lanka.

The writer of Motivation Letter 6 consistently utilized the pronoun “I” as a self-referential element, maintaining a cohesive narrative throughout the letter. Furthermore, the writer employed the possessive pronoun “my” to denote ownership and association with personal activities and belongings. This consistent use of personal pronouns reflects a deliberate choice in crafting a personalized and individualized expression of motivation.

Overall, the writers used present simple as their main tenses for the motivation letters—e.g., examples of present simple tense in Motivation Letter 10 include:

- Moreover, I also have some work experience as an assistant lecturer and private teacher in economics and English.
- I currently work as a marketing staff at . . . , one of the finance companies in Aceh’s province.

The writer of Motivation Letter 10 mostly used present simple as the main tense in the letter. He/she used it to explain about his/her job at the time, the things he/she wanted to do, and the information about the country he/she intended to pursue his/her study in.

In the collective analysis of the motivation letters, a consistent pattern emerged where writers predominantly employed the passive voice as the

primary temporal framework. This trend is exemplified in Motivation Letter 10, where the writer strategically used passive voice throughout the letter. For example:

- Germany is known as among the most innovative countries with abundant research institutions that are directly connected with the university.

The writer of Motivation Letter 10 showed a prevalent use of passive voice, employing it to elucidate various aspects of their professional and academic journey. This voice was notably utilized to describe the writer's current employment, articulate their aspirations and goals, and convey information about the country where they intended to pursue further studies. Their consistent reliance on the passive voice suggests a deliberate choice by the writer to convey information with clarity and directness, contributing to the overall coherence of their motivational narrative.

Moreover, in the analysis of the motivation letters, a notable feature is the widespread use of adverbs, serving as linguistic devices to emphasize and enrich the content. Motivation Letter 10 provides illustrative instances:

- My dream is to become a young businessman who is able to provide benefits for me and for the community, especially Aceh.
- Then indirectly I have contributed to the government to increase economic growth and prosper the community through the availability of jobs.

Motivation Letter 10 prominently incorporates adverbs to underscore specific points throughout the text. The writer employs adverbs of manner, using these linguistic elements multiple times to convey a sense of emphasis and detail in their narrative. This deliberate use of adverbs contributes to a nuanced and expressive tone in the letter, allowing the writer to articulate their aspirations and contributions with heightened clarity and impact. The strategic incorporation of adverbs reflects the writer's skillful use of language to communicate not only facts but also the emotional and qualitative dimensions of their motivations and experiences.

Throughout the analysis of motivation letters, the use of perfect tenses emerged as a notable linguistic feature. This tense was predominantly employed to articulate the writer's past experiences, encompassing areas such as job roles, educational achievements, and volunteer work. In Motivation Letter 6, the use of perfect tense is exemplified:

- Consequently, my academic performance has always been at the top of my class.

Perfect tenses were consistently identified in many motivation letters across the dataset, with a prevalent concentration in Move 1—i.e., Establishing credentials. In this context, writers strategically utilized the perfect tense to provide a detailed and nuanced account of their past accomplishments, highlighting the relevance and significance of their experiences. The deployment of perfect tenses not only serves as a grammatical tool but also contributes to the overall precision and effectiveness of the writers' expressions, allowing them to convey a sense of accomplishment and continuity in their academic and professional journey. This deliberate choice to use perfect tenses in the narrative aligns with the communicative goal of emphasizing the relevance and impact of past experiences on their current motivations and aspirations.

In our comprehensive analysis, the presence of modals emerged as a prevalent linguistic feature across almost all motivation letters in the dataset. This grammatical construct was identified as a significant element in expressing the writers' intentions, aspirations, and expectations. Motivation Letter 5 provides a clear example:

- Finally, with the plan that I have set, the chance to be DAAD-Aceh Scholarship of Excellence Master awardee will not only be beneficial for me but also for others.

Finally, the use of modals—specifically 'will' and 'can'—was widespread in the motivation letters, each serving distinct purposes. In Motivation Letter 5, the writer employed 'will' to articulate their future plans and expectations, emphasizing the positive outcomes they anticipated. This trend was consistent across the dataset, with writers utilizing modals to express their desires, goals, and anticipated outcomes in future endeavors. The strategic use of modals not only adds nuance to the language but also provides insights into the writers' perspectives and attitudes toward their prospective academic and professional journeys. The findings underscore the writers' adeptness in leveraging modals as a linguistic tool to convey a sense of determination, possibility, and purpose in their motivational narratives.

5. Discussion

As for rhetorical structures, the findings revealed that five of the seven rhetorical moves in Bhatia's (1993) model were present in the data: Move 1 (establishing credentials), Move 2 (introducing candidature), Move 4 (enclosing documents), Move 6 (soliciting responses), and Move 7 (ending

politely). Similar to López-Ferrero and Bach (2016), who identified five moves in their research on Spanish motivation letters, the current study also found these moves, though with slightly different names and functions. Moves 3 (offering incentives) and 5 (using pressure tactics) were absent from the data, aligning with Tatsanajamsuk (2017), who noted these moves are more relevant to sales and job application letters rather than motivation letters. Move 3, which offers incentives, is typically used to attract readers in sales promotions, while Move 5 involves pressuring the reader to make a quick decision in job applications—both of which are supposedly irrelevant to motivation letters.

The study observed various patterns in the application of moves within motivation letters. The first variation closely follows Bhatia's (1993) framework, utilizing four to five moves. The second variation used only two moves, predominantly Move 1 (establishing credentials) and Move 2 (introducing candidature). Some letters began with Move 1 and proceeded to Move 2, while others started with Move 2 and included Move 1 or Move 7 (ending politely). In a few cases, only Move 1 was used. Table 1 shows the frequencies of moves in the motivation letters. Despite the presence of five moves, some appeared infrequently. This finding mirrors Wang's (2005) research, where Moves 1, 2, and 3 were more common, although Move 3 was notably rare in this study.

Table 1

Moves in Motivation Letters

Moves	Pattern
Establishing credentials	18
Introducing candidatures	19
Offering incentives	0
Enclosing documents	1
Using pressure tactic	0
Soliciting response	2
Ending politely	4

Move 1, found in 18 letters, was used to detail academic backgrounds and experiences, showcasing candidates' suitability for scholarships. Move 1 emphasizes the candidate's academic strength and can include information about the target location, making it a frequent choice for demonstrating academic prowess. Although Bhatia (1993) refers to "companies," in this context, this move serves to highlight academic qualifications pertinent to

scholarship applications. Move 2—identified in 19 letters—introduces the candidate and provides personal details. This move was the most frequently used, aligning with Wang's (2005) findings. The purpose of Move 2 is to offer a relevant, positive self-description, essential for persuading the scholarship committee (Wang, 2005). It involves three steps: (a) offering the candidature, (b) detailing the candidature, and (c) indicating the candidature's value. While not all writers used every step, they varied in their application of Move 2, with some focusing more on personal details and others on family background.

Move 3 was not present in our data, consistent with its infrequent use in motivation letters (Tatsanajamsuk, 2017). Move 4, found in only one letter, contrasts with Wang's (2005) results, which showed a high frequency of enclosed documents. Similarly, Rahim and Arifin (2014) observed different practices among ASEAN applicants, with varying levels of detail in enclosed documents. Move 5, involving pressure tactics, was also absent, reflecting its irrelevance to motivation letters (Bhatia, 1993; Rahim & Arifin, 2014). Move 6 appeared in two letters, a lower frequency compared to Wang's (2005) study. Move 7, which was found in four letters, shows a low prevalence similar to Wang's (2005) findings and highlights that many writers did not recognize its importance.

Overall, the motivation letters did not consistently follow Bhatia's (1993) move-step structure. Many letters employed Moves 1 and 2, though not always in the prescribed sequence. As noted by Swales (2004), there is variability in the use of obligatory versus optional moves. This research confirms that Moves 1 and 2 are crucial, while the others are less commonly used. Table 2 summarizes the obligatory and optional moves in the motivation letters, with Moves 1 and 2 being identified as obligatory, while Moves 4, 5, and 7 are considered optional.

Table 2
Summary of Obligatory and Optional Moves

Obligatory	Optional
Establishing credentials	Enclosed documents
Offering candidature	Enclosed documents
Step 1: Introducing candidature	Soliciting response
Step 2: Essential detailing of candidature	Ending politely

Note that Salmani Nodoushan (2012, 2023b) has a different categorization for rhetorical moves and their steps which includes three levels: (a) obligatory moves/steps, (b) conventional moves/steps, and (c) optional moves/steps. In an attempt to provide an 'operational' and 'quantifiable' categorization for moves/steps, Salmani Nodoushan (2012, 2023b) has taken the famous 'normal probability curve' in statistics as a guide and has used 'standard deviations' from the 'mean' to develop his categories. As such, any move/step that is observed in 100% of the cases—in our study in all of the 20 motivation letters—is to be called 'obligatory', any move/step observed in 66% to 99.49% of the cases is to be called 'conventional', and any move/step that is seen in less than 66% percent of the cases (i.e., in exactly 65.49%-minus cases) is to be called 'optional'.

Regarding linguistic features, successful applicants ensure their motivation letters are grammatically correct. Allison et al. (2008) emphasize the importance of using simple past, present, progressive, perfect, and perfect progressive tenses. The research identified the use of personal pronouns, present simple, perfect tenses, adverbs, and modals as key linguistic features in effective motivation letters

The use of the personal pronoun 'I' was observed in all of the motivation letters. First-person singular pronouns, including the 'subjective' and 'possessive' cases (i.e., 'I' and 'my') occurred far more frequently than other types of personal pronouns. As part of the reason for the presence of first-person singular pronoun, the writer referred to himself/herself as I, which may suggest an intention to increase personal attributions. Grant and Ginther's research (2000) shows that the most used grammatical structures in academic writing are nouns, pronouns, and verbs. Differentiating the first and the third person is easier if the writer uses personal pronouns. A personal pronoun is one that distinguishes the speaker, the person or thing spoken to, and the person or thing spoken of (Faris & Cheng, 2010). Furthermore, using the personal pronoun can lead the reader to easily grab the main point or ideas.

Advertising or persuasive language commonly uses personal pronouns and that is one of its characteristics. The use of personal pronouns falls within the interpersonal dimension (Labrador et al., 2014). In addition, the second person pronoun is also mostly found to refer to the reader or awardee committee. The use of the second person pronoun contributes to making funders feel the message is directed at them individually and building familiarity (Cruz et al., 2017). Therefore, the use of personal pronouns aims to build a familiar atmosphere between the writer and the reader.

The findings revealed that the highest occurrence frequency of tenses is simple present tense (at 100%) which is present in all of the 20 motivation letters. The simple present tense found in Move 1 and Move 2 is used by the writers to explain the reasons why the candidates were suitable for the program by presenting their achievements, abilities, relevant skills, and experiences that suit the program they are applying to.

Aside from present simple, present progressive tense is also found throughout the motivation letters. It is mostly presented in Move 2 (introducing candidature) to present the candidates' credentials to apply for the prospective positions (Bhatia, 1993). In addition, present progressive, à la Faiza (2012), is used to show the applicants' recognition of the kind of individual the employer seeks in the move of establishing credentials. The writers of the motivation letters used the present progressive tense to elaborate on their current situation as in their education, working experiences, and other activities that can boost their point as strong candidates such as doing volunteer work.

Present simple was also used to describe personal characteristics, strengths, or present job responsibilities. Present simple was also used in Move 4 (enclosing documents) in order to remind the readers to see detailed information regarding qualifications, experiences, interests, and abilities in the resume, certificates, and testimonials which are referred to as the documents attached. Lastly in Move 7 (ending politely), present simple was used to thank the readers for reading the letter.

In light of Bhatia's (1993) framework, present perfect was found in Move 1 which is introducing the candidate at the steps of (a) detailed information of the candidature and (b) indicating the value of the candidature—to highlight, according to Tatsanajamsuk (2017), their work experience and applicants' self-representation. The highest occurrence frequency of present perfect was found in Move 2 which introduces candidature.

Likewise, the writers of the motivation letters in this research used past or perfect tenses to express the most necessary information in the past of the candidatures—for example, qualifications, past experiences, abilities, and achievements attained from the previous work. In this part, the writers used perfect tenses to present more past relevant experiences or achievements they gained from previous jobs.

Adverbs were also found in a good numbers of motivation letters. Almost all of the motivation letters included adverbs. Adverbs also have a big influence in writing as they can help writers elaborate their ideas well. The frequent occurrences of adverbs include adverbs of place, adverbs of time, adverbs of manner, adverbs of frequency, and adverbs of degree (Bhatia, 1993). In academic writing, adverbs can show a variety of rhetorical functions (Hinkel, 2004). The writers mostly used the adverbs to emphasize something he/she expressed in the letter.

Modals were frequently found in the motivation letters. The most frequent one was 'will'. The modal 'can' was also mostly found in the data, but it was not as frequent as 'will'. The last one was 'would' with a small number of occurrences. Recent research has shown modal verb usage in both persuasive and academic writing. 'Can' and 'will' continue to be the most frequently utilized modals in argumentative writing by ESL learners (Kader et al., 2013) and in self-improvement literature (Ahmad Farrag, 2022). Modals play crucial roles in persuasion, with 'will' often used for making predictions and 'can' for indicating possibilities and abilities (Ahmad Farrag, 2022). This observation supports previous studies that identify 'will' and 'can' as prevalent central modals in English (Vine, 2004). Additionally, in educational essays, 'can,' 'may,' 'will,' 'should,' 'would,' and 'must' are the most commonly used modals, reflecting the conventions of academic writing (Riadil, 2020).

6. Conclusion

The results of this research show that all of the motivation letters used the first and second moves, but they were used variably. The other moves such as enclosing documents, soliciting responses, and ending politely are also found in the data but with very low frequencies. Two moves were not found in any motivation letters analyzed in this research. We believe this is caused by (a) cultural diversity and (b) because the functions of these moves are not relevant to motivation letters. Therefore, it can be concluded that the first and second moves which are 'establishing credentials' and 'introducing candidature' are obligatory moves in motivation letters. 'Enclosing documents' (Move 4), 'soliciting response' (Move 6), and 'ending politely' (Move 7) are optional. The linguistic features found in this research were personal pronouns, simple present tense, passive voice, perfect tense, adverbs, and modals. The use of these linguistic features is also related to the moves in the motivation letter itself. Present tense is used throughout the letters and perfect tense is used to explain candidature's past experiences and achievements.

Academic writing is taught in universities but it is not applied to many genres, specifically to motivation letters. Therefore, we would like to suggest that teaching how to write motivation letters should be part of academic writing instruction. This will definitely impart professional writing knowledge to students who will then have the basic skill of writing motivation letters after they graduate from the university.

Authors' Statement

This paper is a collaborative work, which was initially proposed by Siti Sarah Fitriani. Meanwhile, Irmanisa Irmanisa contributed to the data validation and amelioration of the whole manuscript in all sections, and Yunisrina Qismullah Yusuf and Heather Linville provided overall comments on the manuscript and made necessary amendments to fit the aims and scopes of the journal.

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